

BOOST D4.4: NERC DataLabs: A Roadmap to improve Discovery and Access

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Introduction

NERC has managed data access and sharing policies since its creation in 1965. Today, the Environmental Data Service (EDS)¹ provides integrated data services across its five data centres, including operational analysis platforms, across all NERC² domains. Most science applications are becoming increasingly multidisciplinary; The EDS is working towards providing environmental data users with a “one stop shop” for data services. The EDS forms part of NERC’s digital strategy and implementation, working across discipline boundaries to break down barriers and facilitate data sharing.

The EDS, with partners, will pilot cloud native FAIR data services to support cross-disciplinary, pan-UKRI applications which increasingly need to combine diverse data and knowledge of the underpinning measurement and data capabilities. These services will extend our DRI Phase 1b developments of core NERC data services, building on international standards and data commons principles to link to existing cross-council DRI developments. The BOOST project :

- Data findability and traceability through Persistent Identifier registration and asset cataloguing with a novel linking of provenance via semantic graphing techniques.
- Extend data accessibility and interoperability by continuing to develop a federated Trusted Research Environment on JASMIN, ensuring compliance with DARE UK standards.
- Building on the EDS DataLabs data processing environment, create workflow services to process, quality assure and integrate large-scale genomics data that describe biodiversity.
- Enhance interoperability across disciplines by performing a detailed review of analysis platforms across disciplines and user applications, leading to recommendations for FAIR implementation.
- Support all of the above through a coordinated framework of co-creation of services and associated training with users.

This document is concerned with activities on Work Package 4 which performed a review of Analysis Platforms with Recommendations for Interoperation. NERC and UKRI have many data analysis platforms designed to accommodate individual communities, workflows and available resources. We will exploit the RDA³ framework, emerging global trans-disciplinary standards and also develop links with CEOS⁴ and other trailblazing community groups to establish best practice. The recommendations will inform FAIR data services working within a CARE compliant framework⁵.

¹ <https://eds.ukri.org/environmental-data-service>

² <https://www.ukri.org/councils/nerc/>

³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/>

⁴ <https://ceos.org/>

⁵ https://static1.squarespace.com/static/5d3799de845604000199cd24/t/6397b363b502ff481fce6baf/1670886246948/CARE%2BPrinciples_One%2BPages%2BFINAL_Oct_17_2019.pdf

Workpack 4 Deliverables:

- BOOST D4.1: Working Group, Workshops, User Survey and Key Reports
- BOOST D4.2 – Progress with establishing a TRE on JASMIN and utilising workflows - May 9th Workshop
- BOOST D4.3 - CEOS Jupyter Notebooks Best Practice V1.1
- BOOST D4.4 - NERC DataLabs Fair Interoperability (**This document**)
- BOOST D4.5: Inter-platform/archive workflows and use cases for RO-Crates
- BOOST 4.6 - Recommendation for improving the interoperability of Data Analysis Platforms

In this document BOOST D4.4 key aspects of the DataLabs and Discoverability document ⁶ are reviewed in the context of the broader BOOST project.

DataLabs is a cloud-based digital platform designed to support collaborative, open, transparent, and data-driven science. It allows users to flexibly combine multiple elements within one integrated ‘environment’, and for this reason it is sometimes classified as a Virtual Research Environment (VRE). For the avoidance of confusion, DataLabs is the name of both the platform and individual projects (DataLabs within DataLabs). Each project integrates a unique combination of digital assets – data, models, methods, code, visualisations, etc. – which are then used to answer environmental research questions and support decision making.

This document uses as its key source the DataLabs and Discoverability document; A Summary Report on the DataLabs Enhancements Project; David Philip Green, Carolynne Lord, Kelly Widdicks, Jennifer Roebuck, Lily Gouldsbrough, Mike Hollaway, and Gordon Blair. The aim of this short study is to draw out recommendations made in the above document and explore commonalities with other platforms as a basis for future recommendations.

The report states that a key challenge facing DataLabs is that the kinds of digital assets it works with tend to be fragmented, heterogeneous, and inconsistent, and they can be challenging to locate, interpret, and integrate. While some datasets and digital research outputs have a unique domain object identifier (DOI), making them easier to find and work with, most digital assets do not. Asset fragmentation not only obstructs systemic science, it also contributes to a duplication of efforts, as pre-existing research outputs remain undiscovered. We characterise this as a discoverability challenge, one that is slowing the advancement of environmental science, wasting resources, and increasing DRI’s environmental impact (Bird et al. 2023⁷).

⁶ DataLabs and discoverability: a summary report on the DataLabs enhancements project; Green, David Philip ; Lord, Carolynne ; Widdicks, Kelly ; Roebuck, Jennifer; Gouldsbrough, Lily ; Hollaway, Mike ; Blair, Gordon ; <https://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/539039/>

⁷ Bird, C., Priest, C., Lord, C., Friday, A., Widdicks, K., Kayumbi, G., Lambert, S., Jackson, A. (2023). Learning from the Big Picture: Applying Responsible Innovation to the Net Zero Research; [10.5281/zenodo.7948731](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7948731)

In the report, they draw on a two-part study that explores future directions for enhancing discoverability within and through DataLabs: The first part of the study is based on recent engagement with stakeholders in environmental science at UKCEH, conducted as part of a wider co-design strategy to better understand how DRI might be developed in the future. Taking a 'bottom-up' approach, this part of the study explored users' perspectives on DRI and how these infrastructures could be enhanced in the future, including improvements to DataLabs and discoverability. The second part of the study, which reflects a more 'top-down' approach, presents insights from the development of an experimental Large Language Model (LLM) designed to improve the discoverability of digital assets in DataLabs.

Discoverability supports interoperability: the process of finding and identifying relevant resources, data, models, services, etc., is a fundamental prerequisite for this exchange to happen. We will now examine the report aspects that relate most strongly to platform interoperability. We will not deal with aspects related to user centred design or co-creation, as those are catered to well in Work Package 5 outputs.

Survey Findings

In the report, 52.7% of survey respondents 'agreed' or 'somewhat agreed' that environmental science 'data,' 'methods,' and 'models' are currently findable, and 39.2% 'agreed' or 'somewhat agreed' that they were accessible. However, nearly all of participants agreed that they should be made more so, with 86.5% agreeing or somewhat agreeing that they should be more findable and 83.7% agreeing or somewhat agreeing that they should be more accessible.

These findings suggest that existing DRI is working to an extent, but it also demonstrates that there are improvements to be made, and hints at areas where future development of DRI - and DataLabs specifically - could be targeted. For instance, it is notable that data were considered more findable and accessible than methods or models (none of the respondents firmly 'agreed' that models were accessible, for instance), so extra effort may be needed to improve the findability and accessibility of methods and models.

Infrastructure Transformation (ARINZRIT).
<https://zenodo.org/records/7966424/files/ARINZRIT-Final%20Report-23May2023.pdf?download=1>,
accessed April 2024.

In a related BOOST activity a workshop was held with NCEO (an adjacent domain to UKCEH) PhD students at the Rutherford Appleton Laboratory on Wednesday 13th December 2023. We presented the data and the infrastructure ecosystem for Earth Observation on a number of levels. We tested the group's awareness and training needs at each level. The key finding from the workshop was that awareness of data sources with the exception of CEDA, JASMIN and Google Earth was very low.

There was no awareness of the broader EDS data centres or NERC Data Labs. However when the data centres and NERC Data Labs were explained there was genuine interest and potential application in their research areas. The group would like more training on the digital landscape and thought this type of training should ideally begin at undergraduate level. This points to both platform specific and digital landscape training being vitally important.

Discoverability of DataLabs (Platforms, and Assets)

The report observes that broader availability of DRI means that there are many different systems that can be used to achieve similar results. Where teams, or individual researchers, found barriers in their use of DataLabs, or tensions that they struggled to overcome, it was common to switch over to a different system – or to split their use across different systems.

Whilst the financial and environmental cost of digital tools and infrastructures are often hidden from their users, organisationally there is a cost to hosting and maintaining infrastructures which enhance the discoverability of assets. A balance must be struck between the benefits of discoverable assets and the burden of upscaling, supporting, and financing discoverability.

Through the BOOST Data Analysis platform working group we also observed that the main cohort of users on data analysis platforms differs from archive users. This is because UKRI data platform users tend to be established researchers on UKRI funded projects. However we are aware of a much broader audience who need to carry out lighter weight analysis or consumption or training with our datasets. These groups tend to have restricted or limited access to platform based resources. This is why we are making a recommendation that the DAPI working is evolved to include universities and government departments so it can support strategic development of national infrastructure that enables broad and cost effective use of our data.

Culture

The report notes other barriers to discoverability were discussed which are less easily attended to through the design of DataLabs, or through the potentiality of LLMs. Participants noted that the current research culture, and ways of working, limit the discoverability of digital assets in environmental science; especially in the desire of researchers to contribute towards improving this. Discoverability, in short, requires not just technological tools, but also requires resourcing and motivation on the part of researchers to make their research outputs – and the digital assets encompassing these outputs – discoverable.

We observed the issue surrounding Jupyter notebooks in the D4.3 study. The situation has evolved where although Zenodo contains over 1.5 million notebooks the vast majority are simply unusable due to lack of metadata, poor quality and curation. These are important tools which have the potential to break down significant barriers. It is also important that once we have motivated a community that adequate infrastructure is in place to capture these digital assets.

The report also notes that whilst DataLabs aims to make scientific work more discoverable, it must also allow for the privacy and security of assets – and data in particular – that require it. Tools of this type need to have areas that are ring fenced, and users need to be made aware of how to keep their data secure and non-discoverable in new working environments. The study in D4.2 discusses some of early attempts at establishing a TRE on JASMIN. As a community we are in the process of appreciating the complexities of establishing such secure environments on our data analysis platforms. Through the working group other platforms such as DAFNI⁸ and the Earth Observation Data Hub⁹ have developed an interest in establishing such environments on their own platforms. To that end we are continuing to work with DAREUK¹⁰ by holding a workshop on the 9th of May to continue examining the issue.

⁸ <https://www.dafni.ac.uk/>

⁹ <https://eodatahub.org.uk/>

¹⁰ <https://dareuk.org.uk/>

Exploration of LLMs for enhancing asset discoverability

UKCEH also explored a prototype Large Language Model (LLM) as a promising and emerging technological solution that could improve the discoverability of assets. A LLM is a type of artificial intelligence model trained on a vast corpus of data, which allows it to understand and generate text that closely mirrors human language. This capability is not only revolutionizing our interaction with technology but also transforming how we access information. When applied to the field of asset discoverability, LLMs can interpret and facilitate the identification of relevant metadata assets for given user queries. They can help facilitate an intuitive environment for end-users, significantly reducing the need for specialized scientific knowledge during the search for a digital asset.

We should also point out that the issue of vocabularies raised itself repeatedly in the BOOST user survey. The EDS data centres have also long observed that we individually use a range of formal standardised vocabularies such as CF Standard Names¹¹ that we actively promote. The standardized vocabularies also differ from data centre to data centre due to their evolution in different communities. We also have datasets that have ad-hoc project defined vocabularies.

Going outside of the immediate EDS centres we engaged with other sectors through the digital twin hub, data sharing working group. We initiated conversations with Jessica Symons of Visioning Lab¹² who had recently enjoyed success with Human-in-the-loop (HITL) AI in the energy sector working with CReDo¹³. We also continued the conversation with Catherine Jones of the UKERC Energy Data Centre¹⁴ who could see the merits of a project investigating the use of AI across the energy and environmental sectors.

This naturally suggests that a study is required to evaluate merits of Human-in-the-loop (HITL) AI versus Large Language Models (LLMs) in supporting the discovery of EDS data by academic research communities and industry.

¹¹ <https://cfconventions.org/Data/cf-standard-names/current/build/cf-standard-name-table.html>

¹² <https://www.visioninglab.com/>

¹³ <https://digitaltwinhub.co.uk/climate-resilience-demonstrator-credo/>

¹⁴ <https://ukerc.rl.ac.uk/>

Stakeholders

The report notes that enhancing the discoverability of DataLabs and the assets within it requires a better understanding of its users – and potential users. The findings show DataLabs can be difficult to find, and it is relatively unknown in the community, suggesting it is not reaching the stakeholders for whom it is created. Additionally, there will be further stakeholders across UKCEH and in the wider community that are currently not being considered at all. Given the focus of DataLabs is to support collaborative, integrative and systemic science, there will be a wide variety of stakeholders for whom the platform could be useful; we need to engage with these stakeholders more deeply to map their requirements and the science questions that they may wish to answer through enhanced discoverability of assets (via an LLM or traditional metadata searches). These will include scientists, academics, and decision makers such as policymakers (e.g., “what policy should be introduced to control river pollution?”) as well as individual members of the general public (e.g., “is it safe to swim in the River Ribble?”).

The report states the need to better understand the stakeholder landscape in environmental science and uncover which tensions and barriers they face in their work that could be supported through DataLabs or other DRI, and in turn, how we may best engage them through our suggested approach of stakeholder engagement and co-design. Future work should map the landscape of stakeholders across environmental science and its connecting domains, acknowledging that this is a dynamic category; as the science changes, so too do the stakeholders, and the potential application areas for the kinds of science DataLabs supports.

The issue of potential stakeholders is common to all platforms attending the working group. In addition to developing a better understanding of our stakeholders we also need to consider how we compliment each other and avoid unnecessary duplication, as a lot of data analysis platforms were developed in answer to the immediate needs of scientists conducting UKRI funded research. We have long known that data holdings and other valuable research outputs have much greater potential than they are currently realising. Other platforms such as digital twins or those running models on infrastructure may also benefit from data feeds/data transformations from platforms to their own systems. The National DRI ecosystem as a whole also needs to be considered. This will influence key decisions on levels of storage volumes/types, processing, security restricting resources etc. We therefore advocate an evolved working group that encompasses greater stakeholder representation.

Summary

The NERC DataLabs and Discovery report has given valuable insight into NERC DataLabs and the common themes that also occur on other UKRI platforms. We envisage continuing to work with DAREUK¹⁵ by holding a workshop on the 9th of May to continue examining the issue of to best provide secure environments on our platforms. We should investigate the merits of Human-in-the-loop (HITL) AI versus Large Language Models (LLMs) in supporting the discovery of EDS data by academic research communities and industry. The working group should evolve to accommodate stakeholders and other platform providers beyond UKRI.

¹⁵ <https://dareuk.org.uk/>